

PROMOTING THE USE OF LIBRARY COLLECTIONS THROUGH LIBRARY PUBLICITY.

By

YUSUF OLAREWaju IBRAHIM

*Kwara State College of Arabic and Islamic Legal Studies,
Department of Library Science, Ilorin.*

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is simple, it is a provocation. It discusses promoting the use of library collections through library publicity. This paper also shows that any library that is expected to be functioning effectively, the library publicity should not be left out. Because it promotes the use of library collections and projects the image of the library and also creates fruitful understanding between the library and users/expected users. The study was also conducted to intimate the readers on the role public relation has to play to boost library patronage. It dwells much on the ability of public relation to promote, inform and influence

INTRODUCTION

It is obviously through display and library publicity that the libraries attract more users and project the image of libraries. If any library wants to achieve its aims and objectives for its existence, a lot of library activities have to be their functions. Given the definition of library by different researchers, it is a belief that setting up library is also a great challenge and can be made to benefit many generations. Library provides access to information materials and it is a place where. Information is shared which makes the society to move from one level of development to another.

Library have considerable experience dealing with different user which provides the role in supporting efficient library services. This is in providing a trusted services authority based upon librarians making choices, evaluating information as a par collection development and with a thorough understanding of what users need.

**PROMOTING THE USE OF LIBRARY COLLECTIONS
THROUGH LIBRARY PUBLICITY.**

For libraries to achieve the set goals which among others are educating the people and transforming the society, a great function to exercise often is 'publicity'. So, therefore library publicity plays vital roles in promoting the use of library collections.

To make this discussion more comprehensive, the definitions of both terms 'library' and 'publicity' have to be given:

Nwalo, (2003)¹ gave the definition of library as an organization that is primarily set up to acquire, organize, store and make accessible to the users, within the quickest possible times all forms of information materials which they require while the definition of publicity is also given by different researchers. In their attempts, publicity also means public relation. Igbokwe (1997)² quoted Raw and Chandra (1993) defining public relation (publicity) in reporting the world conference of public relationship held in Mexico 1978, as having defined it as the art and social science of analyzing trends, predicting the consequences, counselling organization leaders and implementing planned programme of actions which serve both the organization and public interest.

The institute of public relation (UK) defined public relation as the deliberate planned and sustained efforts to establish and maintain mutual understanding between an organization and its public (Raw and Chandra 1993), quoted by Ahmed (2003)³

With the understanding of the above definitions of publicity (public relation), publicity means public awareness in order to create understanding between an organization and public to project the image of an organization and to attract more customers.

Library publicity means the various activities put forward by the library collection. It can also be defined as any effort carried out to project the image of any given library.

Nwalo (2003) discussed as part of library publicity, all good libraries publish quarterly accessions list and news bulletin. According to him, this publication

*PROMOTING THE USE OF LIBRARY COLLECTIONS
THROUGH LIBRARY PUBLICITY.*

informs patrons of the latest addition to library stock and gives them general news about the library. The news can be transfers; new appointments; merging or demerging of departments; creation of new department: If service time has been extended; materials presentation; new policies and general staff welfare; new materials; etc.

Patrick (1977)⁴ noted in his public knowledge, private knowledge; Toward a library and information policy, libraries are an essential element in the educational system, which is the society's main arrangement for reducing costly ignorance. To those whose occupational function is the search for new knowledge or the application of exiting knowledge to the solution of society problems the library is an indispensable source of information, as they will have at their command a vast array of private, college, university national public school and special libraries.

The reduction of costly ignorance by libraries is achieved through the assistance they provide in the process of formal and non formal education and in the direct assistance they give to scholars and scientists in the extension of the frontiers of knowledge.

Marian (1980)⁵ also noted that the public relation officer stands a better chance of consulting with the best use of the various media for public relation effectiveness. The author stressed that the public relation officer in the library is expected to serve as liaison officer with the friend of the library, organization and the government at large.

Adekunle (1994)⁶ stated that planning is an exercise in scientific thinking and analysis, with particular reference to demands of the public relation profession and of the organization of its environment.

A separate office that holds the responsibility of publicity service should be set aside in library under the responsibility of library public relation officer (library P.R.O). If the responsibility of library publicity is not under a single person called Library P.R.O, then all the library staff should be performing the activities of the library publicity in the absence of an office for library publicity.

As it has been said earlier that publicity and public relation mean the same thing. Public relations is the group of activities or measure undertaken to promote in the public mind a favourable feeling towards a cooperation, institution, product or person.

The primary goal of public relations/publicity is to build and hold good will. The measuring scale of good will is public opinion i.e. the attitude and beliefs of any considerable number of people not necessarily a majority on specific event or issue.

Why Library Publicity: Public relation according to Betty (1982)⁷ "is a way of life. Any institution which hopes to achieve that degree of flexibility and responsiveness to public opinion which will ensure its survival finds public relation a necessity".

Dada (1979)⁸ gave the following reasons for library display;

- a. To inform the potential readers of the library holdings under each subject or discipline.
- b. To stimulate the full exploitation of books and other library materials
- c. To facilitate inter library cooperation by exposing the library stock.
- d. To increase the readership of the library as a way of actively decreasing the illiteracy rate in any given society.
- e. To sustain the interest of the users in the services rendered by the library.

The reasons why public relation/publicity is needed in library are numerous. These reasons are telling us the purposes of public relation/publicity in our libraries. The librarian as a manager of information and public relation officer tries to communicate the essence of the library to appropriate audience. He fight the anti-library in the minds of the public.

Furthermore, for a library to achieve or attain its objectives, it need to embark on certain efforts, endearvour or programme toward promoting the library image. These efforts and or programmes are known as public relation/publicity in library.

**PROMOTING THE USE OF LIBRARY COLLECTIONS
THROUGH LIBRARY PUBLICITY.**

In addition, library publicity, purposefully functions because: To promotes the use of library collection and creates community awareness or patrons (users) awareness on library services in order to establish public understanding on the library. Also to win the moral and financial support of public for the library and create a good feeling or remark of the public for the library, by improving the library in satisfying further needs of the users including making the library and its collection with activities to be more recognized.

Library Public Relation Officer:

Most libraries in Nigeria do not specifically have library 'public Relation officer' (P-R-O). The system of having no library P-R-O tends to be criticized as it is only efficient having library public Relation officer. Instead, the circulation units serve and hold the responsibilities of the library P-R-O. A library with library P-R-O, has the great advantages over those libraries that do not have.

It is never easy to throw things away, and sometimes it is difficult to decide which system is functional. But there is an increasing emphasis on the use of library public Relation officer which I believe that no library can afford to neglect this library publicity.

As it has been said earlier in Nigeria most of the available libraries do not specifically have Library P-R-O unlike in abroad. Examples among others that have library public Relation officers are, University of Ilorin library, University of Ibandan of Library, Kwara State CAILS Library, Bayero University library, Kano.

A public relation officer is a person or an officer that is primarily responsible for the promotion of the organization activities in projecting the image of that organization and attract more customers for the organization. The library P.R.Q. is described as a library staff to promote or facilitate the activities of library. The library publicity i.e. public relation is under the function of the library public relation officer (Library P.R.O). The functions of the library publicity are derived as a result of the programmes, activities planned by the library P.R.O.

For any library to achieve the expected reasons for library publicity, it is no doubts that the library public relation officer holds the following responsibilities among others:

Library P.R.O. goes outside the confines of the library to carve a good image of their establishment in the minds of the potential patrons. A good number of libraries offer commercial printing, photocopying binding and consultancy services. It is the duty of the library P.R.O. to inform the public about these services. The library P.R.O. informs the patrons of the latest addition to library stock, the library P.R.O. gives the patrons/users the general news about the library. The library P.R.O. publishes or informs people on library notice board or bulletin board. He/she advises the library management or authority, the library P.R.O. is responsible for, enlightenment or orientation for the library users. Library P.R.O. is an intermediary between the library and the library user he/she gives answers to the patrons questions promotion of good relationship between the library and the public in press media he/she is responsible for the library publications coordination the library P.R.O. also writes the library report he/she organize every programme that can protect the image of the library or that promotes the use of the library.

Communication: - A message is transferred from one person to another i.e. from one end to another end. The system of transmitting or transferring this message is known as 'communication'. On the understanding, the person that passes the message is called the 'Encoder' otherwise known as (transmitter) while the person or party that receives the information is called the 'Decoder' otherwise known as receiver. Summarily, communication is the transmission and reception of message. When a message is passed it means information has taken place (Ahmed and Yusuf 2006)⁹

There are four 4 basic elements of communication and these are:

1. Encoder transmitter
2. The message
3. The medium used in transmitting the message

4. The Decoder Receiver

Through communication we are informed, through information we are developed. In librarianship a good communication is essential for the progress of any library. The library is an intermediary between the world of knowledge (Books and Non-Books) and the users. So therefore, if there is no communication between the library and the users, the users cannot be informed on anything. Henceforth, an effective communication is needed in library services for library (librarians) to be able to communicate the available information to the appropriate users. For this to be done effectively, there will be knowledge on 'publicity' or 'public relation', which will facilitate the library services.

The communication affects the library services positively or negatively. That is library practices or services depend on how effective the library and communication is: for this reason, in the library publicity processing, the library P. R. O. should be very careful in common charting with the public or users. Ahmed (2004) gave the following as the factors affecting the communication.

The language of library P.R.O. communication must be simple and understood, if not, no communication. There should be clarity in the language used in communication by the library P.R.O., because it determines the success of communication in attracting users to using library materials. The message should be briefed for quick understanding. The appropriate medium should be used in communication. Among the mediums that can be used in transferring message are: newspapers, television, radio, oral, textbooks and etc. Attention i.e. (attentiveness) also affects the communication. The message transmitter needs the attention of the message recipient or receiver to avoid misunderstanding in the communication, interest of the message transmitter and message receiver matter in communication.

All these given above, are major factors to be considered by any library P.R.O. for library and public/user communication for library publicity, While if the absence, the library services will not be effective as expected.

Library Publications For Publicity;

One of the functions of a library P.R.O. is that he/she co-ordinates the library publications for the library publicity. Examples of these publications for the library publicity are: handbills, promotional, handouts, posters, film coverage, journal and also books can be published to enhance library publicity or library public relation. The media like newspapers, radio television, are also parts of library publications for library publicity. Orientation programmes are also organized for the public to promote the understanding of the library services in the minds of the public to protect the image and to promote the use of the library.

Creation of library publicity materials such as sign, bulletin, boards, exhibitions, special displays, posters are also used in library publicity. These six are known as 'visual publicity'.

Signs:

The signs should be available for those who need them in the library telling them where to go and where no to go in the library, either to have access to certain thing or not in the library, is smoking cigarettes allowed or not in the library, to make noise, fight or not, and switching on or off the handsets in the library etc.

Bulletin Boards:

A bulletin can be regarded as a short notice or brief information that is meant to disseminate to the public. Boards may be constructed of cellulose, wallboard, Pegboard, flannel, plywood, or cork etc. Cellulose and Pegboard are the most easily available ones. Any board that contains such information is referred to as Bulletin Board. A fixed bulletin board may be any specifications. It is well to frame it simply but strongly and to paint the board itself to make the board more attractive. Among other type of Bulletin boards is moveable bulletin board which can also add much to the library. A popular design is the folding and placed at angles to each other. When not in use they may be folded together for storage (Obi 1997).

Exhibition And Displays:

The library public relation officer should always help his library and its collection to, be more effective by arranging displays of books man open place particularly in connection with tropical events. A display should never be too large 20 books or 15 are quit adequate, otherwise there is a tendency for the books to be overlooked which should be avoided. it should, be kept continually fresh and the books replenished.

In the context of librarianship, exhibition and displays can be referred to as the techniques or methods of exposing the various library materials for the attention of the users community.

Library displays and exhibitions have almost identical meaning, library displays are mounted for several reasons.

- (1) To reveal the resources of the library
- (2) To aid the students and supplement the teaching programme by displaying books and materials which may be particularly useful to a particular class.
- (3) To impact information, teach a lesson or express an idea
- (4) To increase circulation (students coming to circulation)-
- (5) To raise reading standings by guiding students to select better or more varied books

Everyone likes to see new books. This is why the displaying is very essential and it facilitates teaching and learning in our academics.

The displays areas include;

- (1) Display in show windows (some libraries have inbuilt show windows for the purpose of library displays). These show windows could be at the entrance halls or corridors on the outside wall of the library.
- (2) Display in the entrance hall.
- (3) Display in special areas-modern libraries are so well designed that a separate accommodation is created for library displays. Library users are guided to this apartment, which is well decorated and illuminated.

(4) **Mobile displays** this could be done on vans on which are mounted display stands. Mobile display tend to reach out the people who are far away from the library building require close supervision and security.

Display furniture Obi (1977)¹⁰ have highlighted divers items of display furniture, while include bulletin boards. Library chalkboard is also an example of display furniture.

Posters:

A poster requires a few moments of attention. This means that the messages that the posters carry are meant to seen and absorbed quickly. Posters give brief information about something. A poster tells the public about the library programmes and its services and the available material. The posters should be attractive. The specific library products, services, events are advertised in the posters. These is done to promote the library publicity.

These visual publicity are established and coordinated by the library public relation Officer to enhance library publicity in order to promote the use of library collection.

Problems Hindering Carrying Out Library Public Relation Job

(a) **Insufficient fund:** enough money is required in carrying out effective public relation. But the library budget is so low. Extral fund is needed to solve this problem.

(b) **The management or parent establishment support:** if the library management is not convinced of what the library publicity is all about, the aims and objectives for the publicity will not be achieved. There is a need for convincing the library management and motivate users by encouraging better use of the library by different categories of people.

The problems among others facing public relation in library are given by this paper and solutions followed immediately are provided by this paper.

Conclusion:

Library publicity is unseperated from the library functions. Because of the vital roles it has in making the library to be able to achieve its set objectives and goals why the library is established. Any living library without library publicity is like an organization having tangible products produced by its organization consequently. But which has little or no customers, due to no communication or advertisement informing the potential buyers or general public what the organization has for the society.

A library is not a commercial organization aiming towards profit making otherwise. The focus of the library(s) is growth and development deviwur. To have effective library services, it demands for library publicity which results to good outcome. The library publicity has made library(s) known and more relevant to its users and expected users.

Recommendation

The libraries should continue struggling striving to satisfy their users and try to improve in their services and library publicity. In the minds of some people they don't have positive feelings for the libraries because of their ignorance to what libraries are all about. This paper appreciates the efforts of the libraries embarking on library publicity and encourages other libraries to emulate this.

Enough funds should be made available to the library public relation officer(s) to enable him/her (them) carryout his duties. Apart from the financial support, the provision of other necessary library facilities to assist the library P.R.O. should be given by the library, and even the' parent establishment of the particular library to boost the library services.

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